

Voltammetric Behaviour of Pyridine-2-aldoxime

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D.c. polarography, cyclic voltammetry, a.c. polarography, differential pulse polarography (dpp), rotating ring disk voltammetry, millicoulometry and controlled potential electrolysis have been employed for the study of electrochemical reduction behaviour of pyridine-2-aldoxime (PyAl). The universal buffers of pH ranging from 2 to 12 are used as supporting electrolytes. Kinetic parameters such as diffusion coefficient (D) and heterogeneous forward rate constant ($k_{f,h}^0$) values are evaluated and reduction mechanism is proposed on the basis of the results obtained. Dpp is employed for the analysis of the compound.

Several papers have been devoted to the electrochemical study of the oximes of heterocyclic carbonyl compounds¹. Three isomeric oximes of formylpyridines give irreversible four-electron wave for the protonated form, the height of which decreases at pH > 10. The oximes of 2- and 4-formylpyridine iodide also give a wave of the deprotonated compound in alkaline media, i.e. two-electron wave corresponding to the reduction of the amino-methylpyridine. Reddy and Gurrappa² earlier carried out the electrochemical investigations of certain pyridine oxime derivatives employing the modern electrochemical techniques. In the present investigation, a thorough electrochemical study of PyAl (I) is made with a view to get more information on the reduction mechanism and the electrode kinetics concerned employing advanced electrochemical techniques, such as d.c. polarography, cyclic voltammetry, a.c. polarography, differential pulse polarography, rotating ring disk voltammetry, millicoulometry and controlled potential electrolysis.

Results and Discussion

PyAl is found to give a well-defined single d.c./a.c. polarographic wave or c.v. peak in the pH range 2-4 (Figs. 1 and 2). An additional wave/peak is

Fig. 1 Typical d.c. polarogram of pyridine-2-aldoxime at pH 2; concn = 0.5 M, drop time = 3 s.

noticed at pH 8. But in dpp two adjacent waves/peaks in the place of single wave/peak observed in other techniques, are obtained as shown in Fig. 3.

The two adjacent waves/peaks are attributed to the reduction of *syn* and *anti* forms of PyAl respectively. The *syn* form (*a*) has the pyridinic nitrogen protonated and an intra-molecular hydrogen bond with the oxime group is formed through this proton. As a result, the *syn* form gets reduced at more anodic potential. In the *anti* form (*b*), this incipient

Fig. 2. Typical cyclic voltammogram of pyridine-2-aldoxime at pH 12; concn = 0.5 mM, scan rate = 40 mV s⁻¹

Fig. 3. Typical differential pulse polarogram of pyridine-2-aldoxime at pH 2; concn = 0.5 mM, drop time = 2 s.

bond is not possible due to the previous existence of a hydrogen bond between the pyridine nitrogen and the hydroxylic hydrogen with the formation of a six-membered stable ring that makes necessary the participation of proton from the solution for the formation of the intermediate imine compound. Thus the reduction of *anti* form becomes more difficult.

The first wave observed is confirmed as due to the 4e⁻ reduction to the formation of amine derivative. The additional wave observed in the alkaline

solution is attributed to the cleavage of the amino group from methylpyridine in a two-electron process.

All the electrode processes involved are found to be diffusion-controlled and adsorption-free in the buffer systems studied as shown by the linear plots of i_d vs $h^{1/2}$, i_p vs $v^{1/2}$ and I_{1d} vs $w^{1/2}$ without intercept. The irreversible nature of the electrode process is confirmed by log-plot analysis and slope value exceeds 59.2/ n mV. The plot of the i_m vs $(1-\sigma)/(1+\sigma)$ is found to be non-linear and a.c. summit potential observed to deviate from the d.c. polarographic half-wave potential indicating the electrode process to be irreversible. The number of electrons involved in the electrode process as determined by millicoulometry is found to be four for the oxime group in the acidic media (pH 4) and two for the first and second waves in the basic media (pH 10). Controlled potential electrolysis has been carried out in a pH 6 at -0.75 V (vs SCE) and the reduced product was isolated and confirmed through ir spectral studies (nujol; 3 300, 1 600 cm⁻¹).

The kinetic parameters such as diffusion coefficient and heterogeneous forward rate constant values are evaluated from the various techniques and reported in Table 1. The diffusion coefficient values evaluated from all the techniques are in good agreement. But diffusion coefficient values evaluated from the rotating ring disk voltammetry are found to be higher than the other techniques due to the fact that the convection transport of the depolariser to the electrode in the former technique, is likely to play a very prominent role.

In general, the heterogeneous forward rate constant ($k_{f,h}^0$) values evaluated using all the techniques decrease with increase in pH of the supporting electrolyte. The rate constant values responsible for the oxime group reduction are found to be high in the acidic medium. This indicates that the rate of reaction is fast in acidic media as compared to that in the basic media, since in the acidic media highly reactive protonated form gets reduced in contrast to the less reactive deprotonated form in the basic media. The rate constant values evaluated in a.c. polarography are found to be higher than those obtained from other techniques. This is because the

TABLE 1—KINETIC DATA OF PYRIDINE-2-ALDOXIME

Supporting electrolyte	D.C. Polarography			Cyclic voltammetry			A.C. Polarography			Differential polarography			Rotating ring disk voltammetry	
	$-E_{1/2}$	$D \times 10^3$	$k_{f,h}^0$	$-E_p$	$D \times 10^3$	$k_{f,h}^0$	$-E_s$	$D \times 10^3$	k_s	$-E_m$	$D \times 10^3$	$k_{f,h}^0$	$D \times 10^5$	$k_{f,h}^0$
	V	$\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	cm s^{-1}	V	$\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	cm s^{-1}	V	$\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	cm s^{-1}	V	$\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	cm s^{-1}	$\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	cm s^{-1}
2.0* (iA)	0.32	-	-	0.34	-	-	0.35	-	-	0.33	-	-	-	-
(iB)	0.40	-	-	0.42	-	-	0.43	-	-	0.41	-	-	-	-
4.0* (iA)	0.44	-	-	0.46	-	-	Distorted peak		0.45	-	-	-	-	-
(iB)	0.55	-	-	0.55	-	-			0.55	-	-	-	-	-
6.0	0.66	8.53	5.13×10^{-11}	0.63	8.01	6.12×10^{-10}	0.61	7.98	9.14×10^{-7}	0.59	8.10	3.32×10^{-11}	9.08	5.22×10^{-9}
8.0 (a)	0.82	8.10	6.75×10^{-12}	0.82	7.85*	1.19×10^{-12}	0.79	7.65	7.12×10^{-9}	0.70	8.02	1.17×10^{-13}	9.01	5.22×10^{-13}
(b)	1.52	8.29	5.19×10^{-17}	1.51	8.15	2.97×10^{-18}	Merging with hydrogen evolution			1.45	7.85	2.48×10^{-17}	8.69	7.19×10^{-13}
10.0 (a)	1.08	7.92	1.23×10^{-16}	1.05	7.77	4.15×10^{-15}	1.02	7.28	1.55×10^{-11}	0.99	7.60	6.92×10^{-16}	8.78	5.15×10^{-14}
(b)	1.61	8.22	113.77×10^{-19}	1.63	8.01	5.77×10^{-20}	1.59	7.11	4.17×10^{-15}	1.52	7.52	8.01×10^{-20}	8.23	1.87×10^{-19}
12.0 (a)	1.22	7.61	4.91×10^{-19}	1.16	7.52	7.21×10^{-19}	1.17	7.19	3.15×10^{-14}	1.10	7.28	3.15×10^{-20}	8.40	2.13×10^{-15}
(b)	1.71	8.19	2.50×10^{-23}	1.72	7.65	2.22×10^{-23}	1.69	7.08	6.73×10^{-18}	1.68	7.21	6.49×10^{-21}	7.93	5.27×10^{-21}

*Two overlapping waves (iA, iB) are observed.

(a) First wave. (b) Second wave.

rate constant values are evaluated at standard potential in a.c. polarography, and in other techniques these are calculated at potential $E=0$ magnitude and nature of the charge transfer kinetic contribution to the frequency may also matter in a.c. technique.

On the basis of the above results, the following reduction mechanism may be proposed for PyAl.

In acidic media ($2 \leq \text{pH} \leq 6$), the reduction mechanism is the same for both isomers and 2-aminomethylpyridine is formed as a product with overall interchange of four electrons,

In basic media ($8 \leq \text{pH} \leq 12$), the following reactions occur :

where R is pyridyl.

Analysis : In the present investigation, differential pulse polarography has been used for the qualitative estimation of PyAl using the current obtained for the oxime group reduction. Here the appearance of the two adjacent waves in the acidic media makes the analysis of the compound difficult. Due to the nonavailability of protons in the basic media, the wave obtained is not well-resolvable and well-defined to carry out the analysis in this media. Consequently, the analysis is carried out in the region $6 \leq \text{pH}$

≤ 10 , in which well-resolved peaks are observed. Differential pulse polarography is employed for elucidating analytical procedures for the estimation of PyAl using both calibration and standard addition methods. The peak current is found to vary linearly with concentration of the compound over the range 1.5×10^{-5} to $2.8 \times 10^{-7} M$ at pH 6; the lower detection limit is found to be $2.65 \times 10^{-7} M$. The best precision is obtained with drop time of 2 s and pulse amplitude of 50 mV (potential = $-0.6V$). The standard deviation and correlation coefficient (for 10 replicants) are found to be 1.25% and 0.993 respectively.

Experimental

A polarograph (PARC 364) coupled with a BD 8 Kipp and Zonen X-t recorder was used for d.c. polarographic measurements. A potentiostat (AFRDE 4) and speed control unit (MSRX) (Pine Instrument Co., U.S.A.) coupled with a X-Y/t recorder (Digital Electronics 2000) were used for rotating disk as well as rotating ring disk voltammetric measurements. Other measurements were carried out using a Polarecord (Metrohm E506) coupled with E612 VA-scanner, E608 VA-controller, E648 VA-combistand and above X-Y/t recorder. All electrochemical measurements were carried out using a conventional three-electrode design at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The dropping mercury electrode (area 0.2223 cm^2) and hanging mercury drop electrode (area 0.0328 cm^2) were used as working electrodes. Reference electrodes employed were

Ag/AgCl (S) Cl^- electrode for cyclic voltammetry, a.c. polarography and differential pulse polarography and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) for d.c. polarography. A platinum electrode was used as the counter electrode to complete the electrolytic circuit. A modified cell with a mercury pool cathode, SCE, a platinum wire gauge electrode and a spot galvanometer, was used for controlled potential electrolysis.

PyAl (Sigma) was used as such. Universal buffers (pH 2 to 12) were prepared using 0.2 M boric acid, 0.05 M citric acid and 0.1M trisodium orthophosphate. All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The test solution was purged with oxygen-free nitrogen gas for 10 min before the voltammograms were taken. For controlled potential electrolysis, PyAl (~ 100 mg) was dissolved in a minimum amount of triple-distilled water and required amount (25–40 ml) of the supporting electrolyte (pH 6) added.

Procedure : The supporting electrolyte of pH 6 is a suitable medium for the analysis. A standard

solution of PyAl (1.0×10^{-4} M; 1 ml) was transferred to a polarographic cell and made up to 10 ml with the supporting electrolyte to get a concentration of 1×10^{-5} M and then deoxygenated by bubbling nitrogen. After taking the polarogram, the standard solution of the PyAl was added in small increments (0.2 ml) and polarogram recorded after each addition under similar condition. From this the unknown concentration of the sample was calculated.

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